

An Insight into the Capabilities of Professionals and Teams in Agile Software Development - An Updated Review [Supplementary Material]

The first part of this document (Appendix A) presents the list of Systematic Literature Review (SLR) primary studies, followed by (Appendix B) the attributes identified to measure individual and team capabilities used in our survey.

APPENDIX A: LIST OF SLR PRIMARY STUDIES

- [P1] Emilia Mendes, Davi Viana, Sai Datta Vishnubhotla, and Lars Lundberg. 2018. Realising individual and team capability in agile software development: a qualitative investigation. In 2018 44th Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA). IEEE, 183–190.
- [P2] Sai Datta Vishnubhotla, Emilia Mendes, and Lars Lundberg. (2021). Understanding the perceived relevance of capability measures: A survey of Agile Software Development practitioners. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 180, 111013.
- [P3] Nana Assyne, Hadi Ghanbari, and Mirja Pulkkinen. 2022. The essential competencies of software professionals: a unified competence framework. *Information and Software Technology*, 151, 107020.
- [P4] Lucas Gren, Alessia Knauss, and Christoph Johann Stettina. 2018. Non-technical individual skills are weakly connected to the maturity of agile practices. *Information and Software Technology*, 99, 11–20.
- [P5] Antonio Alexandre Moura Costa, Felipe Barbosa Araújo Ramos, Mirko Barbosa Perkusich, Arthur Silva Freire, Hyggo O Almeida, and Angelo Perkusich. 2018. A Search-based Software Engineering Approach to Support Multiple Team Formation for Scrum Projects. *SEKE*, 474–473.
- [P6] Mawarny M Rejab, James Noble, and Stuart Marshall. 2019. Agile self-selecting teams foster expertise coordination. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Information, Knowledge, and Management*, 14, 99.
- [P7] Israt Fatema and Kazi Sakib. 2018. Using qualitative system dynamics in the development of an agile teamwork productivity model. *International Journal on Advances in Software*, 12, 11, 170–185.
- [P8] Fernando Almeida, Diogo Adão, and Catarina Martins. 2019. Decision support system for assigning members to agile teams. *International Journal of Information Technologies and Systems Approach (IJITSA)*, IGI Global, 2, 12, 43–60.
- [P9] Christiaan Verwijs, and Daniel Russo. 2021. A theory of scrum team effectiveness. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.12439*.
- [P10] M. Rizwan Jameel Qureshi and Zahra Abass. 2017. Long Term Learning of Agile Teams. *International Journal of Software Engineering & Applications (IJSEA)*, 6, 8.
- [P11] Luís Felipe Amorim, Marcelo Marinho and Suzana Sampaio. 2020. How (un) happiness impacts on software engineers in Agile teams?. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.03546*.
- [P12] Murat Yilmaz, Rory V O’Connor, Ricardo Colomo-Palacios and Paul Clarke. 2017. An examination of personality traits and how they impact on software development teams. *Information and Software Technology*, Elsevier, 86, 101–122.
- [P13] Vanja Čatić Kuko, Denis Mušić, Zanin Vejzović and Jasmin Azemović. 2019. Model of foresight work habits of agile software team members by personality traits. 2019 International Conference on Computer, Information and Telecommunication Systems (CITS), IEEE, 1–5.
- [P14] Emily Weimar, Ariadi Nugroho, Joost Visser, Aske Plaat, Martijn Goudbeek and Alexander P Schouten. 2017. The influence of teamwork quality on software team performance. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1701.06146*.
- [P15] Anna Wiedemann, Manuel Wiesche, and Helmut Krcmar. 2019. Integrating development and operations in cross-functional teams-toward a devops competency model. In *Proceedings of the 2019 on Computers and People Research Conference*, 14–19.
- [P16] Diane Strode, Torgeir Dingsøyr and Yngve Lindsjorn. 2022. A teamwork effectiveness model for agile software development. *Empirical Software Engineering*, Springer, 2, 27, 1–50.
- [P17] Abirami Radhakrishnan, Jigish Zaveri, Dessa David and John Stephen Davis. 2022. The impact of project team characteristics and client collaboration on project agility and project success: An empirical study. *European Management Journal*, Elsevier, 5, 40, 758–777.
- [P18] Fadilah Rifa’ah, Teguh Raharjo, Bob Hardian, Agus Suhanto, Rufina Fitri Anjani, et al. 2022. People factors influencing project success in software development: a survey of agile development teams in indonesia. In *International Conference on Science and Technology Innovation (ICoSTEC) number 1*. Vol. 1, 109–116.

APPENDIX B: OVERVIEW OF SELECTED STUDIES.

TABLE I: Overview of primary studies.

S.ID	Attr. level	Attr. type	Meas. met.	Predic	Ctx.
[P1]	Team/Indiv.	Hard/Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P2]	Team/Indiv.	Tech./Social	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P3]	Indiv.	Hard/Soft	N/D	N/D	Acad./Ind. [P1]
[P4]	Indiv.	Social	N/D	L.R.M.	Ind.
[P5]	Indiv.	Technical	Experience	N/D	Ind.
[P6]	Team	Tech./Social	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P7]	Team	Hard/Soft	Sys. dyn.	N/D	Ind.
[P8]	Team	Tech./Social	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P9]	Team	Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P10]	Team	Tech./Social	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P11]	Team	Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P12]	Indiv.	Soft	Inter. asses.	N/D	Ind.
[P13]	Indiv.	Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P14]	Team	Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P15]	Team	Hard/Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P16]	Team	Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P17]	Team	Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.
[P18]	Team	Hard/Soft	N/D	N/D	Ind.

APPENDIX C: ATTRIBUTES FOR CAPABILITY MEASURE.

TABLE II: Individual engineer attributes; category: Innovative

Sub-category	Capability measure	Description	S.ID
Creativity	Attention to detail	The quality of achieving thoroughness and accuracy when accomplishing a task through concern for all the areas involved.	[P2]
	Creative problem solving	The ability to find a solution to a problem by using imagination or original and unusual ideas	[P2]
	Critical thinking	The ability to think carefully about a subject or idea, without allowing feelings or opinions to affect the individual	[P2]
	Generating ideas	The ability to create ideas	[P2]
	Synthesis/reorganization	The ability to combine a number of different parts or ideas to come up with a new idea or theory	[P2]
Enterprising	Gathering and evaluating information	The ability to gather and evaluate relevant information	[P2]
	Identifying problem	The ability to recognize a problem	[P2]
	Independent thinking	The ability to make sense of things based on one's own experiences and observations. Trust one's own ability to make judgements	[P2]
	Seeking improvement	The quality of trying to acquire, gain or achieve improvement	[P2]
	Technological savvy	Well informed about or proficient in the use of modern technology	[P2]
Integrating perspectives	Openness to ideas	The tendency to accept new ideas, methods or changes	[P2]
	Research orientation	The quality of being inquisitive, problem-oriented along with critical thinking and creative working	[P2]
	Collaborating	The ability to work jointly with others or together especially in an intellectual endeavor	[P2]
Forecasting	Engaging in non-work related interest	The ability to engage with others in non-work-related interests	[P2]
	Evaluating long-term consequences	The ability to evaluate long-term consequences of a task or problem	[P2]
	Visioning	The act or the power of imagination	[P2]
	Managing the future	To exert control over or regulate the events likely to happen at a later time	[P2]
Managing change	Sensitivity to Situations	The quality of understanding the situations and being careful not to do anything that harms or damages it	[P2]
	Challenging the status quo	To behave or do something in a way contrary to that which is generally accepted or expected	[P2]
	Intelligent risk-taking	Acting under conditions where key variables and potential outcomes are unknown and could be negative, but where risk is required to achieve superior outcomes	[P2]
	Reinforcing change	The ability to strengthen or support change	[P2]
	Ability to optimize existing solutions/systems		[P2]

TABLE V: Attributes for team; category: Innovative

Sub-category	Capability measure	S.ID
Creativity	Openness to creativity	[P11]
	Task variety/ Innovation	[P7]
	Creative exploration and exploitation	[P2]
Managing change	Agile adaptation	[P11]
Foresight	Foresight skill	[P2]

TABLE VI: Attributes for team; category: Professional

Sub-category	Capability measure	S.ID
Agile capability	Team Velocity	[P1]
	Responsive to needs of stakeholders	[P9]
	Software development quick	[P18]
	On-time Project completion	[P17]
	Conscious sensitivity	[P2]
	Responsiveness to customer	[P2]
Growth	Environment needs and changes	[P2]
	Continuous improvement	[P9]
	Continuous integrating tools	[P8]
	Active learning and improvement	[P2]
Business excellence	Advancement	[P2]
	Mutual performance monitoring	[P7]
	Effectiveness	[P2]
	Result-orientation	[P2]
Operational excellence	Systemic benefits	[P2]
	Sustainable efficiency	[P2]
Software security	Consistent predictability	[P2]
	Testing	[P8] [P15]
Team experience	Big data	[P8]
	Customer experience	[P2]
	Database	[P8]
	Domain knowledge	[P2] [P15]
	Generational experience	[P2]
	Pair programming	[P7]
	Programming language	[P2] [P7]
Tools usage	[P2] [P7]	
Miscellaneous	Aligned expectations	[P11]
	Meeting project specifications	[P17]
	Backup behavior	[P7]
	Challenging environment	[P11]
	Constant evolution	[P11]
	Concern with stakeholder needs	[P9]
	Diversity	[P1][P6] [P17]
	Cultural issues	[P1]
	Competent team architect	[P1]
	Peer Feedback	[P16]
	Shared leadership	[P16]
	Backup Behaviour/redundancy	[P16]
	Team Orientation	[P16]
	Freedom to choose	[P11]
	Inclusion on decisions	[P11]
	Reuse	[P7]
	Resource constraints	[P7]
Self managing	[P7]	

TABLE VII: Attributes for team; category: Social

Sub-Category	Capability measure	S.ID
Social	Adaptability	[P7] [P16] [P17]
	Collaborative members	[P11]
	Coordination	[P7]
	Communication	[P2] [P7] [P11] [P16]
	Confidence	[P11]
	Motivation	[P2] [P7][P11]
	Mutual trust	[P7] [P16]
	Proactive members	[P11]
	Problem solving	[P8] [P15] [P17]
	Team Leadership	[P7] [P16]
	Team autonomy	[P9] [P17]
	Knowledge Dissemination	[P10]
	Team member rotation	[P10]
	Customer Collaboration	[P10] [P17]
	Catching Recurrent Information	[P10]
	Team Reflection	[P10]
	Coordination of Expertise	[P14]
	Value Sharing	[P14]
	Trust	[P14]
	Socio-relational	[P15]
	Commitment	[P18]
	Interpersonal adaptability	[P17]
	Handling work stress	[P17]
	Morale	[P2]
	Value diversity	[P2]
	Internal competition	[P2]
	Cooperation	[P2]
	Cohesion	[P2]
Preference to work with	[P6]	

TABLE IX: Comparative study: Professional individual attributes

Sub category	Attribute	Our study	OSLR
Software quality	Delivered quality	✓	
	Productivity	✓	
	Test and Quality engineering	✓	
	Maintenance	✓	
	Product audits	✓	✓
	Statistical control	✓	✓
Software construction	Current implementation track record	✓	
	Debugging and testing	✓	✓
	Detailed design and coding	✓	✓
	Integrating and collaborating	✓	✓
	Managing software construction	✓	✓
	Software Development	✓	
	Programming language	✓	
	Software design	✓	
	Site Reliability Engineering	✓	
	System integration and verification	✓	✓
	System validation and deployment	✓	✓
	System sustainment planning	✓	✓
	Software construction planning	✓	✓
	Proficiency in code reviewing	✓	
Software requirements	Elicitation	✓	✓
	Documentation	✓	
	Project Management	✓	✓
	Requirements analysis	✓	✓
	Specification	✓	✓
	Validation	✓	
	Verification	✓	✓
Software design	Fundamentals	✓	✓
	Quality analysis and evaluation	✓	✓
	Software architectural design	✓	✓
	Strategies and methods	✓	✓
Software system engineering	Concept definition	✓	✓
	Component engineering	✓	✓
	Requirements allocation	✓	✓
	System life cycle modeling	✓	✓
Software process model and life cycle model	intensive systems engineering	✓	✓
	Assessment and improvement	✓	✓
	Definition and tailoring	✓	✓
	Implementation and management	✓	✓
Human-computer interaction	Development life cycle models	✓	✓
	Accessibility	✓	✓
	Interaction style design	✓	
	Requirements	✓	✓
Software testing	Usability testing	✓	✓
	Visual design	✓	✓
	Techniques	✓	✓
	Planning	✓	✓
Software sustainment	Infrastructure	✓	✓
	Measurement and defect tracking	✓	✓
	Software transition	✓	✓
	Software support	✓	✓
Software security and safety	Software maintenance	✓	✓
	Design	✓	✓
	Construction	✓	✓
	Quality	✓	✓
	Requirements	✓	✓
Manage releases	Testing	✓	✓
	Process	✓	✓
Software configuration	Plan software measurement	✓	✓
	Perform software measurement	✓	✓
	Management	✓	✓
	Plan software configuration	✓	✓
Miscellaneous	Conduct software configuration	✓	✓
	Manage software releases	✓	✓
	Accurated effort estimation	✓	
	Application domain knowledge	✓	
	Allocated full-time	✓	✓
	Development/Programming experience	✓	✓
	Prior work experience	✓	✓
	Planning skills	✓	✓
Years in company	✓	✓	
	Proficiency in local language for communication	✓	
	Work pace	✓	

TABLE X: Comparative study: Social individual attributes

TABLE XI: Comparative study: Innovative individual attributes

Sub category	Attribute	Our study	OSLR	Sub category	Attribute	Our study	OSLR
Affective	Aptitude	✓	✓	Creativity	Attention to detail	✓	✓
	Person's attitudes	✓	✓		Creative problem solving	✓	✓
	Person's initiative	✓	✓		Critical thinking	✓	✓
	Planning skills	✓	✓		Generating ideas	✓	✓
	Teamwork	✓	✓		Synthesis/ reorganization	✓	✓
	Leadership	✓	✓	Enterprising	Gathering and evaluating information	✓	✓
	Enthusiasm	✓	✓		Identifying problem	✓	✓
	Work ethic	✓	✓		Independent thinking	✓	✓
	Willingness	✓	✓		Seeking improvement	✓	✓
	Trustworthiness	✓	✓		Technological savvy	✓	✓
	Team participation skills	✓	✓	Integrating perspectives	Openness to ideas	✓	✓
	Self-reliance	✓	✓		Research orientation	✓	✓
Technical leadership skills	✓	✓	Collaborating		✓	✓	
Communication	Communication	✓	✓		Engaging in non-work related interest	✓	✓
	Oral communication	✓	✓		Evaluating long-term consequences	✓	✓
	Listening skills	✓	✓	Forecasting	✓	✓	
	Questioning skills	✓	✓	Managing the future	✓	✓	
Interpersonal	Customer orientation	✓	✓	Managing change	Sensitivity to Situations	✓	✓
	Collaboration	✓	✓		Challenging the status quo	✓	✓
	Cooperation	✓	✓		Intelligent risk-taking	✓	✓
	Interpersonal relation	✓	✓		Reinforcing change	✓	✓
	Handling and solving conflicts	✓	✓	Personal	Introverts and Extroverts	✓	✓
	Seeks help	✓	✓		Intuition and Sensing	✓	✓
	Helps others	✓	✓		Thinking and Feeling	✓	✓
	Attitude	✓	✓		Judging and perceiving	✓	✓
Teamwork oriented	✓	✓	Formal Education		✓	✓	
Willingness to confront	✓	✓	Decision making		✓	✓	
Personal	Problem solving	✓	✓		Business minded	✓	✓
	Development in job environment	✓	✓		Organization	✓	✓
	Openness	✓	✓		Negotiation skills	✓	✓
	Conscientiousness	✓	✓		Ability to meet project goals	✓	✓
	Agreeableness	✓	✓		Development in job environment	✓	✓
	Neuroticism	✓	✓		Openness	✓	✓
	Driven by desire to contribute	✓	✓		Conscientiousness	✓	✓
	Charisma	✓	✓		Agreeableness	✓	✓
	Tenacity	✓	✓		Neuroticism	✓	✓
	Behavior	✓	✓		Driven by desire to contribute	✓	✓
	Knowledge	✓	✓		Charisma	✓	✓
	Education	✓	✓		Tenacity	✓	✓
	Pride in quality and productivity	✓	✓		Behavior	✓	✓
	Perseverance	✓	✓		Knowledge	✓	✓
	Desire to improve things	✓	✓	Education	✓	✓	
	Pro-active/ initiator/ driver	✓	✓	Pride in quality and productivity	✓	✓	
	Maintaining "big picture" view	✓	✓	Perseverance	✓	✓	
	Desire to do/bias for action	✓	✓	Desire to improve things	✓	✓	
	Thoroughness	✓	✓	Pro-active/ initiator/ driver	✓	✓	
	Sense of mission	✓	✓	Maintaining "big picture" view	✓	✓	
	Strength of convictions	✓	✓	Desire to do/bias for action	✓	✓	
	Mixes personal and work goals	✓	✓	Thoroughness	✓	✓	
	Pro-active role with management	✓	✓	Sense of mission	✓	✓	
	Work ethics	Flexibility	✓	✓	Strength of convictions	✓	✓
		Time management	✓	✓	Mixes personal and work goals	✓	✓
		Motivation to work	✓	✓	Pro-active role with management	✓	✓
Commitment		✓	✓	Flexibility	✓	✓	
Responsibility		✓	✓	Time management	✓	✓	
Integrity/ honesty/ ethics		✓	✓	Motivation to work	✓	✓	
Ability to adapt to changing technologies		✓	✓	Commitment	✓	✓	
Task prioritization	✓	✓	Responsibility	✓	✓		

TABLE XII: Comparative study: Professional attributes for team

Sub category	Attribute	Our study	OSLR
Agile capability	Team Velocity	✓	
	Responsive to needs of stakeholders	✓	✓
	Software development quick	✓	
	On-time Project completion	✓	
	Conscious sensitivity	✓	✓
	Responsiveness to customer	✓	✓
	Environment needs and changes	✓	✓
Growth	Continuous improvement	✓	
	Continuous integrating tools	✓	
	Active learning and improvement	✓	✓
	Advancement	✓	✓
Business excellence	Mutual performance monitoring	✓	
	Effectiveness	✓	✓
	Result-orientation	✓	✓
	Systemic benefits	✓	✓
Operational excellence	Sustainable efficiency	✓	✓
	Consistent predictability	✓	✓
Software security	Testing	✓	
Team experience	Big data	✓	
	Customer experience	✓	✓
	Database	✓	
	Domain knowledge	✓	✓
	Generational experience	✓	✓
	Pair programming	✓	
	Programming language	✓	✓
	Tools usage	✓	✓
	Miscellaneous	Aligned expectations	✓
Meeting project specifications		✓	
Backup behavior		✓	
Challenging environment		✓	
Constant evolution		✓	
Concern with stakeholder needs		✓	
Competence Diversity		✓	
Cultural issues		✓	
Competent team architect		✓	
Peer Feedback		✓	
Shared leadership		✓	
Backup Behaviour/redundancy		✓	
Team Orientation		✓	
Freedom to choose		✓	
Inclusion on decisions		✓	
Reuse		✓	
Resource constraints		✓	
Self-managing		✓	
Schedule pressure		✓	
Visible tasks		✓	
Well defined process		✓	
Shared mental models		✓	
Responsibility assumption		✓	
Meet customer's needs		✓	
Technical expertise		✓	✓
Project success rating		✓	
Clear goals		✓	✓
Full-time allocation		✓	✓
Team buy-in		✓	✓
Types of work		✓	
Ability to make decisions		✓	
Knowledge sharing		✓	

TABLE XIII: Comparative study: Social attributes for team

Sub category	Attribute	Our study	OSLR
Social	Adaptability	✓	
	Collaborative members	✓	✓
	Coordination	✓	
	Communication	✓	✓
	Confidence	✓	✓
	Motivation	✓	✓
	Mutual trust	✓	
	Proactive members	✓	✓
	Problem solving	✓	✓
	Team Leadership	✓	
	Team autonomy	✓	
	Knowledge Dissemination	✓	
	Team member rotation	✓	
	Customer Collaboration	✓	
	Catching Recurrent Information	✓	
	Team Reflection	✓	
	Coordination of Expertise	✓	
	Value Sharing	✓	
	Trust	✓	
	Socio-relational	✓	
	Commitment	✓	
	Interpersonal adaptability	✓	
	Handling work stress	✓	
	Morale	✓	✓
	Value diversity	✓	✓
	Internal competition	✓	✓
	Cooperation	✓	✓
	Cohesion	✓	✓
	Preference to work with	✓	

TABLE XIV: Comparative study: Innovative attributes for team

Sub category	Attribute	Our study	OSLR
Creativity	Openness to creativity	✓	
	Task variety/ Innovation	✓	
	Creative exploration/ exploitation	✓	✓
Managing change	Agile adaptation	✓	
Foresight	Foresight skill	✓	✓

TABLE III: Individual engineer attributes; category: Professional

Sub-category	Capability measure	Description	S.ID
Software quality	Delivered quality		[P1]
	Productivity		[P1]
	Test and Quality engineering		[P3]
	Maintenance		[P3]
	Product audits		[P2]
Software construction	Statistical control		[P2]
	Current implementation track record		[P1]
	Debugging and testing		[P2]
	Detailed design and coding		[P2]
	Integrating and collaborating		[P2]
	Managing software construction		[P2]
	Software Development		[P1]
	Programming language		[P3][P5]
	Software design		[P3]
	Site Reliability Engineering		[P15]
	System integration and verification		[P2]
	System validation and deployment		[P2]
	System sustainment planning		[P2]
	Software construction planning		[P2]
Proficiency in code reviewing		[P2]	
Software requirements	Elicitation		[P2]
	Documentation		[P3]
	Project Management		[P3]
	Requirements analysis		[P2] [P3]
	Specification		[P2]
	Validation		[P3]
Software design	Verification		[P2] [P3]
	Fundamentals		[P2]
	Quality analysis and evaluation		[P2]
	Software architectural design		[P2]
Software system engineering	Strategies and methods		[P2]
	Concept definition		[P2]
	Component engineering		[P2]
	Requirements allocation		[P2]
	System life cycle modeling		[P2]
Software process model and life cycle model	intensive systems engineering		[P2]
	Assessment and improvement		[P2]
	Definition and tailoring		[P2]
	Implementation and management		[P2]
Human -computer interaction	Development life cycle models		[P2]
	Accessibility		[P2]
	Interaction style design		[P2]
	Requirements		[P2]
	Usability testing		[P2]
Software testing	Visual design		[P2]
	Techniques		[P2]
	Planning		[P2]
	Infrastructure		[P2]
Software sustainment	Measurement and defect tracking		[P2]
	Software transition		[P2]
	Software support		[P2]
Software security and safety	Software maintenance		[P2]
	Design		[P2]
	Construction		[P2]
	Quality		[P2]
	Requirements		[P2]
Manage software releases	Testing		[P2]
	Process		[P2]
Software configuration	Plan software measurement		[P2]
	Perform software measurement		[P2]
	Management		[P2]
	Plan software configuration		[P2]
Miscellaneous	Conduct software configuration		[P2]
	Manage software releases		[P2]
	Accurated effort estimation		[P1]
	Application domain knowledge		[P1]
	Allocated full-time		[P2]
	Development/Programming experience		[P1] [P2]
	Prior work experience		[P2]
	Planning skills		[P2]
Years in company		[P2]	
	Proficiency in local language for communication		[P2]
	Work pace		[P2]

TABLE IV: Individual engineer attributes; category: Social

Sub-category	Capability measure	S.ID
Affective	Aptitude	[P2]
	Person's attitudes	[P1] [P2]
	Person's initiative	[P1] [P2]
	Planning skills	[P2] [P4]
	Teamwork	[P3] [P4]
	Leadership	[P2] [P4]
	Enthusiasm	[P2]
	Work ethic	[P2]
	Willingness	[P2]
	Trustworthiness	[P2]
	Team participation skills	[P2]
	Technical leadership skills	[P2]
Self-reliance	[P2]	
Communication	Communication	[P4]
	Oral communication	[P2]
	Listening skills	[P2]
	Questioning skills	[P2]
Interpersonal	Customer orientation	[P2] [P4]
	Collaboration	[P4]
	Cooperation	[P3]
	Interpersonal relation	[P3]
	Handling and solving conflicts	[P3]
	Seeks help	[P2]
	Helps others	[P2]
	Attitude	[P2]
	Teamwork oriented	[P2]
	Willingness to confront	[P2]
Personal	Introverts and Extroverts	[P2] [P13]
	Intuition and Sensing	[P2] [P13]
	Thinking and Feeling	[P2] [P13]
	Judging and perceiving	[P2] [P13]
	Formal Education	[P1]
	Decision making	[P4]
	Problem solving	[P4]
	Business minded	[P4]
	Organization	[P4]
	Negotiation skills	[P4]
	Ability to meet project goals	[P4]
	Development in the job environment	[P3]
	Openness	[P2] [P12]
	Conscientiousness	[P12]
	Extroversion	[P12]
	Agreeableness	[P2] [P12]
	Neuroticism	[P12]
	Driven by desire to contribute	[P2]
	Charisma	[P2]
	Tenacity	[P2]
	Behavior	[P2]
	Knowledge	[P2]
	Education	[P2]
	Pride in quality and productivity	[P2]
	Perseverance	[P2]
	Desire to improve things	[P2]
	Pro-active/ initiator/ driver	[P2]
	Maintaining "big picture" view	[P2]
	Desire to do/bias for action	[P2]
	Thoroughness	[P2]
	Sense of mission	[P2]
	Strength of convictions	[P2]
Mixes personal and work goals	[P2]	
Pro-active role with management	[P2]	
Work ethics	Flexibility	[P2]
	Time management	[P2]
	Motivation to work	[P2]
	Commitment	[P2]
	Responsibility	[P2]
	Integrity/ honesty/ ethics	[P2]
	Ability to adapt to changing technologies	[P2]
Task prioritization	[P2]	

TABLE VIII: List of software engineering domains

Domains	Study ID
E-commerce	[?], [?]
Finance/Banking	[?], [?], [?], [?], [?], [?]
Mobile	[?], [?]
E-learning/Education	[?], [?], [?]
Embedded systems	[?]
Logistics/Shipping	[?]
Government Applications	[?], [?], [?], [?], [?]
Entertainment/ Recreation	[?]
Automotive	[?]
Infrastructure services	[?], [?], [?]
Telecommunication	[?], [?], [?], [?]
Internet/Web	[?], [?], [?], [?]
Media and social networking	[?], [?], [?]
Human resources	[?]
Medical/ health	[?], [?], [?]
Biotechnology	[?]
Security Application	[?]
Accounting	[?]
Energy	[?]
Commercial automation	[?], [?], [?]
Agribusiness	[?]
Engineering/Construction	[?]
Software Aerospace	[?]